

Documentation

FAIR metrics extension for geospatial data

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Motivation

Providing researchers with FAIR, coherent, and open access to geospatial data developing innovative approaches for Earth System Sciences and related multidisciplinary use cases. Here, we provide a *FAIR metrics profile for geospatial data*, implemented as an extension for the FAIRsFAIR metrics.

Developing the profile was motivated by the following drivers:

- **GeoDCAT-AP activities** - The application profile is particularly interesting for metadata management in governmental geospatial data repositories that play a crucial role in NFDI4Earth's aims towards the FAIRness of Earth System Science data. Version 3.0 was released in October 2024.
- **NFDI4Earth-developed services implementations** - The Knowledge Hub uses DCAT/GeoDCAT-AP to model dataset metadata harvested from different data sources. The metadata is discoverable in the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All¹.
- **NFDI4Earth Label** - The label is designed to assess the FAIRness and interoperability of Earth System Sciences repositories. The label implements a self-assessment and an automated FAIRness assessment using the F-UJI service on repositories' metadata samples.
- **Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) activities** - The OGC addresses the demands for an internationally usable GeoDCAT standard and thus formed a GeoDCAT Standard Working Group (SWG). NFDI4Earth developers agreed to support the group actively. The 2024 Metadata Code Sprint initiated by the SWG facilitated the implementation of GeoDCAT use cases.
- **NFDI4Earth FAIRness use case** - The metadata code sprint use case combined experiences from the NFDI4Earth-developed services and label implementations with standardisation and recommendation efforts.
- **Further community activities** - Several community catalogues of domain-related projects already implement DCAT/GeoDCAT-AP. The metadata catalogue² of the research project KlimaKonform³ was a use case to evaluate the proposed metrics.

¹ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>

² <https://klimakonform-dmp.geo.tu-dresden.de/>

³ <https://klimakonform.uw.tu-dresden.de/>

Metrics

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F2-01M-GSD
Metric Name	Metadata includes descriptive core elements to support data findability using spatio-temporal characteristics
Description	In addition to FsF-F2-01M, the following metadata core elements should be made available to support spatio-temporal data findability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • geographical coverage implemented as Location (bbox Literal or Geometry) • temporal coverage implemented as Period of Time
FAIR Principle	F2. Data are described with rich metadata
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	see FsF-F2-01M
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • see FsF-F2-01M • Metadata includes spatial coverage as defined in GeoDCAT-AP • Metadata includes temporal coverage as defined in GeoDCAT-AP
Assessment	<p>Check if the geographical and temporal coverage elements exist.</p> <p>Validate the correctness of the temporal coverage, in particular valid date and interval specifications.</p> <p>Validate the correctness of the spatial coverage, in particular the correct specification using WKT, GML, KML or GeoJSON as well as a valid bounding box.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical coverage in GeoDCAT-AP: https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#Dataset.geographicalcoverage • Temporal coverage in GeoDCAT-AP https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#Periodoftime • Metadata recommendations and example: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604586 • FAIRsFAIR metrics: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ymkzVmF_BJmKTQZO0SRQ1YQJaPxefIJZ84AKUJUIGeM/edit?tab=t.0 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • / 	

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-I1-02M-GSD
Metric Name	Metadata uses geospatial semantic resources to specify reference system
Description	As an extension of FsF-I1-02M, a part of the metadata document incorporates information about the spatial reference system using the OGC EPSG Coordinate Reference Systems Register that unambiguously describes the EPSG content so it can be processed automatically by machines.
FAIR Principle	I1. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	see FsF-I1-02M
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata includes reference system as defined in GeoDCAT-AP ● List of EPSG codes
Assessment	<p>Check if the reference system element exists.</p> <p>Validate the correctness of the reference system against the OGC EPSG Coordinate Reference System Register.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reference system in in GeoDCAT-AP: https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/930/releases/3.0.0/#referenceSystem ● OGC EPSG Coordinate Reference Systems Register: https://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/ ● Metadata recommendations and example: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604586 ● FAIRsFAIR metrics: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ymkzVmF_BJmKTQZO0SRQ1YQJaPxefIJZ84AKUJUIGeM/edit?tab=t.0 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● / 	

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.3-01M-GSD
Metric Name	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the Earth System Sciences community
Description	<p>To support data reusability, metadata for geospatial data should be made available following ESS-community-endorsed standards.</p> <p>Criteria for potential community standard candidates address:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - legal constraints, e.g., INSPIRE, high-value datasets - mappings to discipline-agnostic standards - requirements to understand the content of the data, e.g. dedicated fields to spatial and temporal information <p>The identified candidates to describe geospatial data include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO19115 - GeoDCAT-AP
FAIR Principle	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	see FsF-R1.3-01M
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata is available via endpoint ● Metadata includes schema information
Assessment	<p>Gather all metadata standards used by the data repository, filter discipline-agnostic standards.</p> <p>Request one metadata entry available with the above-mentioned standards and validate for compliance.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Geographical coverage in GeoDCAT-AP: https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#Dataset.geographicalcoverage ● INSPIRE legislation: https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/legislation_en ● High-value dataset implementation regulation: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/138/oj ● Mappings: https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#inspire-and-iso-19115-mappings ● Validation: https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#validation-of-geodcat-ap ● Metadata recommendations and example: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604586 ● FAIRsFAIR metrics: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ymkzVmF_BJmKTQZO0SRQ1YQJaPxefIJZ84AKUJUIGeM/edit?tab=t.0 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● / 	

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F4-01M-GSD
Metric Name	Metadata is offered in a ESS-community endorsed standard and machine-readable format
Description	<p>Metadata for geospatial data should be made available through a metadata harvesting protocol or web service.</p> <p>For geospatial data potential candidates include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) - Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Catalog Service for the Web
FAIR Principle	F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	see FsF-F4-01M
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata identifier ● Metadata provision endpoint
Assessment	<p>The following methods may be applied to determine if metadata of the data is accessible programmatically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check if the endpoint returns metadata records as defined ● Check if a search engine friendly reference is embedded in the landing page
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC): https://stacspec.org/en ● Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Catalogue Services: https://www.ogc.org/publications/standard/cat/ ● Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)API Records ergänzen: https://ogcapi.ogc.org/records/overview.html ● Metadata recommendations and example: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604586 ● FAIRsFAIR metrics: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ymkzVmF_BJmKTQZO0SRQ1YQJaPxefIJZ84AKUJUIGeM/edit?tab=t.0 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● / 	